

Alkali Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with Oxygen Donor Ligand—Isatin.

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Isatin (indole-2, 3-dione) shows lactam and lactim structures and in the solid state lactam variety predominates. Mixed ligand complexes of isatin and metal salts of organic acids (glycine, β -alanine, isonitrosoacetophenone, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, α -picolinic acid, *o*-nitrophenol and 8-hydroxyquinoline) of Li, Na and K have been synthesised and their structures investigated, with particular regard to the co-ordination sites.

And by comparing the donor properties of isatin and its two methyl derivatives (N—methylisatin and O—methylisatin), it has been found that in these alkali metal adducts, isatin retains the lactam structure.

ONE of the most fascinating features of chemistry of 'tautomeric ligands' is the variety of ways in which their *keto-enol* (or lactam-lactim) anions can bond to metallic atoms to give varied molecular structures; and we are extending our studies with oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands which exhibit preferential *keto-enol* structure while co-ordinating with different alkali metals, under different conditions.

Isatin (indole-2,3-dione) shows lactam and lactim structures, and in the solid state lactam variety predominates. Isatin presents one of the oldest of tautomerism, and reacts in the lactam form (I) or lactim form (II).

In the present work, mixed ligand complexes of isatin and metal salts of organic acids (glycine, β -alanine, isonitrosoacetophenone, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, picolinic acid, *o*-nitrophenol and 8-hydroxyquinoline) of lithium, sodium and potassium have been synthesised and their structures investigated with particular regard to their co-ordination sites.

Results and Discussion

Our usual method of preparation was to make a concentrated solution of the alkali metal salts in absolute ethanol and add to it the second ligand— isatin. The mixture was warmed and on cooling the adducts separated of the general formula ML_n . Isatin, where HL=the organic acids, M=Li, Na and K; the number of isatin molecule in the adducts has always been one ($n=1$).

All the complexes of isatin are coloured crystalline compounds. These complexes are slightly soluble in most polar solvents, but are insoluble in

non-polar solvents. These complexes are rapidly hydrolysed by exposure to moisture, but are stable when kept in vacuo or in dry, oxygen-free atmosphere.

No conclusion can be drawn from examining the action of heat on complexes which appear to either decompose or undergo a transformation at a temperature slightly lower than the melting point of the second ligand (isatin). The analysis and physical properties of these complexes are given in the Table 1.

The infra-red spectra of all the compounds have been measured in the region $4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Nujol mulls. The selected absorption bands are given in Table 2.

In cyclic lactams the N—H frequency is at 3440 cm^{-1} when free and 3175 cm^{-1} (dimeric structure) when associated. The N—H stretching frequency of isatin just like cyclic lactams, show a broad absorption at 3180 cm^{-1} , suggesting association and a dimeric lactam structure.

That these adducts are not simple physical mixtures of the two components is shown by examining the infra-red spectra, which differ markedly from a physical mixture of the two components. All these adducts have bands between $2600-3150\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are missing in both the components with the exception of K.1N2N.Isatin and K.1NAP.Isatin, where the band is at 3180 cm^{-1} . The N—H band in M.8HQ.Isatin complexes, is shifted down to 3140 cm^{-1} in case of Li, 3120 cm^{-1} for Na and 3070 cm^{-1} for K; while for the rest of the complexes, the band is shifted down to the region $2620-2710\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands could be assigned to a N—H...O absorption, which would account for the absence of N—H absorption above

TABLE—1
 SOME PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA.

Compound	Colour	Transition temp. or Decomposition temp. (°C)	Found (%)				Calculated (%)			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
Li8 HQ. Isatin	Yellow	245 d	67.31	4.49	8.85		68.45	3.69	9.39	
Na8 HQ. Isatin	Yellow	200 d	63.85	3.82	8.22	6.85	64.93	3.50	8.51	7.31
K 8 HQ. Isatin	Pale yellow	170 d	59.92	4.80	8.25	11.60	61.81	3.33	8.48	11.81
K1N2N. Isatin	Dark brown	155 d	61.30	4.54	7.42	10.15	60.33	3.07	7.54	10.89
KONP. Isatin	Yellowish brown	160 d	52.31	3.41	8.40	11.65	51.85	2.74	8.33	12.03
NaPicA. Isatin	Deep yellow	160 d	56.83	4.02	9.20	9.10	57.53	3.08	9.58	9.87
K PicA. Isatin	Yellow	140 t	55.02	3.85	8.78	11.80	54.54	2.92	9.09	12.33
NAGly. Isatin	Deep pink	215 d	50.25	4.31	10.78	8.75	49.13	3.68	11.06	9.42
K Gly. Isatin	Deep pink	210 d	45.30	4.15	10.48	14.25	46.15	3.46	10.76	15.00
LiAln. Isatin	Yellowish green	98 d	52.89	4.79	11.25		54.54	4.54	11.57	
NaAln. Isatin	Yellowish green	93 d	50.20	4.85	10.52	8.20	51.16	4.26	10.71	8.91
K Aln. Isatin	Yellowish green	90 d	46.97	4.66	9.98	13.65	48.17	4.01	10.20	14.23
NaINAP. Isatin	Reddish brown	130 t	59.40	3.23	8.20	6.85	60.37	3.45	8.80	7.23
KINAP. Isatin	Reddish brown	115 t	56.80	3.54	7.98	10.90	57.48	3.29	8.38	11.79

Where, 8 HQ=8-Hydroxyquinoline, 1N2N=1-Nitroso-2-naphthol; ONP=O-Nitrophenol, PicA=Picolinic Acid; Gly=Glycine; Aln= β -Alanine; & INAP=Iso-nitrosoacetophenone.

3150 cm^{-1} . The presence of the above bands in the adducts leaves little doubt that the proton is located in the ring nitrogen of the ligand and is hydrogen bonded (N...H...O). The strong bands found in the complex under investigation in 1700-1750 cm^{-1} regions are assigned to C=O vibrations. The C=O frequency of isatin is split into 1746 (s) and 1726 (sh) cm^{-1} and the lower location of the latter is again due to the formation of hydrogen bond. These two bands have been found to be metal sensitive, with a shift of 10-15 cm^{-1} , as will be clear from the Table 2. The shift towards the lower frequency in C=O suggests that the co-ordination has taken place through oxygen of the C=O group and consequently the bond order of carbon to oxygen has decreased.

TABLE—2

Compound	Selected IR absorption band (cm^{-1})		
	NH—Stretch	C=O	
		I (Free)	II (associated)
Isatin	3180 br	1746	1726
Li 8 HQ. Isatin	3140	1710 sh	1700
Na 8 HQ. Isatin	3120	1725 sh	1705
K 8 HQ. Isatin	3070	1725 sh	1700
K1N2N. Isatin	3180	1730	1715
KONP. Isatin	2670	1735 sh	1720
NAPicA. Isatin	2620	1730 sh	1720
KPicA. Isatin	2660	1725 sh	1715
NaGly. Isatin	2710	1730	1720
KGly. Isatin	2710	1720 sh	1695
LiAln. Isatin	2640	1720	1710
NaAln. Isatin	2680	1725	1718
KAln. Isatin	2700	1722	1708
NaINAP. Isatin	2710	1720 sh	1710
KINAP. Isatin	3180 br	1740 sh	1720

It has also been observed that green coloured alkali metal salts (ML) of 1N2N usually formed brown adducts (ML.n.HL') with other organic acids

(HL')¹; these ligands invariably have a replaceable proton and formed hydrogen bonding. But when the second ligand is devoid of any replaceable proton² (e.g., 1,10-phenanthroline), the adduct retained the green colour of the corresponding 1:1 salt. Isatin adducts of 1N2N formed brown adducts, suggesting again hydrogen bonding by the replaceable proton. Similar observations were noted in the case of M.ONP.Isatin adducts, when the red colour of M.ONP changed to yellowish brown in the isatin adducts after hydrogen bonding.

Isatin in absolute ethanol reacts with sodium ethoxide forming N-sodium salt. The replaceable proton attached to ring nitrogen is easily replaced by sodium metal. This easily replaceable proton of the ring nitrogen of isatin, formed hydrogen bonding with the metal salts of the organic acids.

Another feature of these adducts is that the anion L (the first ligand) must be capable of chelation to form 5- or 6-membered ring. Although *m*-nitrophenol has a high pK (=8.18), compared to ONP (=7.17), which favours adduct formation, no adduct was formed by an alkali metal salt of this with isatin, implying that preliminary chelation by the metal is essential for adduct formation.

Two methyl derivatives of isatin III and IV have been synthesised³, and the complexing ability of these two derivatives with alkali metal salts of the

same acids were looked into. The preparative conditions remaining same, as that of the isatin adducts, we have not been able to synthesise any adduct with O-methylisatin (III), whereas under similar condi-

tions N-methylisatin (IV) formed analogous compounds as that of isatin. But N-methylisatin also did not form any isolable solid adducts with alkali metal salts of 1N2N and ONP, although characteristic colour change was observed, as shown in Table 3. The physical properties of N-methylisatin are given in Table 3.

hour. After filtration, the coloured solution was concentrated and then allowed to cool in a refrigerator. After 24 hours the corresponding adducts of the alkali metal salts with isatin separated out, which were filtered, washed with cold absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80° (Not all did yield solid adducts)

TABLE-3

Compound	Colour	Transition or Decomposition temp (°C)	Selected i r absorption band (C=O)
N-methyl Isatin	Red	130 (m p)	1750 sh 1730
Li 8 HQ NM Isatin	Pale yellow	240 d	1704 1692
Na 8 HQ N M Isatin	Yellowish brown	225 d	1710
NaGly NM Isatin	Light pink	220 d	1710
NaAln NM Isatin	Deep yellow	95 d	1708
NaPicA NM Isatin	Yellowish brown	190 d	1710

The decomposition temperatures of N-methylisatin complexes except Na.Aln NM Isatin are higher than the isatin complex, showing their greater stability. Further, the C=O stretching bands of N-methylisatin complexes have been observed to be metal sensitive (Table 3), with appreciable shift of ca 40 cm⁻¹, suggesting that co-ordination has been through the two carbonyl oxygens. Infra-red studies also indicate that the hydrogen bonding is not an essential feature for forming these compounds.

Thus by comparing the donor properties of isatin and its two methyl ethers, it has been found that in the adducts, isatin retains the lactam structure and resemble those of the pseudo N-methyl ether.

Experimental

A. Adducts of alkali metal salts of 8HQ, 1N2N, ONP, INAP, PicA, Gly and Aln with Isatin

To a saturated ethanol solution of alkali metal (Li, Na and K) salts of the acids (as mentioned above), solid isatin was added (mole ratio 1 : 3). The mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for an

B. Adducts of alkali metal salts of the above mentioned acids with N- and O-methylisatin

The complexes of the alkali metal salts of the above mentioned organic acids with N-methylisatin, were prepared by the method entirely analogous to that described above. However, no adduct separated (and no colour change observed) when tried with O-methylisatin under similar conditions.

References

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